

Bank Heterogeneity, Chief Executive Officer (CEO) Attributes and the Value Relevance of Accounting Information in Nigerian Banks.

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Abstract

This research assessed the interconnectedness between bank heterogeneity, chief executive officer's attributes and the value relevance of accounting information of commercial banks in Nigeria. The study utilized secondary data that were obtained from the financial statements of 11 commercial banks relevant authorization license. The data used covered a period of 5 years (2018 – 2022). Three specific objectives and research questions were advanced and the relevant null hypotheses were postulated in the course of the study, and were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in the study and both the descriptive and inferential statistical tests were conducted on the data obtained from the annual reports of the sampled banks. Based on the test of hypotheses, it was found that both bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes exert individual and joint significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information of commercial banks in Nigeria. This underscores the level of compliance with relevant global best practices and the resilience of Nigeria's commercial banks amidst economic turbulence. Based on these outcomes, it was recommended that commercial banks should always align the selection of CEOs with their specific strategic objectives and capitalize on their CEOs' unique strengths and attributes to drive competitive advantage and enhance value relevance. In addition, banks should invest in continuous training and professional development for CEOs and top management, focusing on emerging financial trends, regulatory changes, and ethical leadership. This will help align CEO decisions with the long-term interests of the bank and its stakeholders. The study thus contributes to knowledge by providing insights on financial disclosures regarding CEO attributes and bank-specific characteristics which can equally help investors and analysts better assess the potential impact of CEO attributes and bank heterogeneity on financial performance and value relevance.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The financial sector remains a cornerstone of economic development, with banks serving as its most critical institutions. In Nigeria, the banking industry has undergone extensive transformation driven by regulatory reforms aimed at improving stability, transparency, and operational efficiency (Inim, Njogo & Oladele, 2019; Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018). Despite these reforms, the sector remains markedly heterogeneous, with banks differing substantially in size, ownership structure, managerial practices, technological capacity, and market positioning. This heterogeneity is more than a structural feature; it has far-reaching implications for financial reporting practices and, ultimately, for the value relevance of accounting information.

Bank heterogeneity refers to the variations in organizational characteristics and operational dynamics across banks. These variations arise from differences in institutional maturity, ownership configuration, risk appetite, governance mechanisms, and geographic reach. In Nigeria's mixed banking landscape which comprise of dominant long-established banks

alongside emerging and agile entrants, these distinctions shape strategic orientations, risk management policies, and financial outcomes.

On the other hand, leadership characteristics add an additional layer of complexity. A growing body of literature highlights the pivotal role of Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) in shaping financial performance, disclosure quality, and organizational direction (Gupta & Mahakud, 2020; Souhir & Amal, 2022; Ukavwe & Jeroh, 2024; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024). CEO attributes such as educational attainment, industry experience, tenure, and managerial orientation are especially consequential in the banking sector, where strategic decisions occur in a highly regulated and information-dense environment. In Nigeria, where banks operate amid regulatory shifts and macroeconomic volatility, the influence of CEO characteristics on financial reporting outcomes has become increasingly salient. Yet, how these attributes interact with bank-level heterogeneity to affect the value relevance of accounting information remains insufficiently understood.

Noteworthy, value relevance is a core metric in financial reporting research, reflecting the usefulness of disclosed information for equity valuation and investment decisions (Ogieh & Jeroh, 2023). In emerging markets such as Nigeria, where there are possible cases of information asymmetry amidst uneven regulatory enforcement, the determinants of value relevance thus require close examination. Although previous studies have explored bank characteristics and managerial traits independently, limited empirical evidence addresses their combined influence on the informativeness of financial statements in the Nigerian banking sector. This gap is critical given the sector's centrality to the economy and its sensitivity to leadership quality and institutional attributes.

Against this backdrop, the present study investigates the joint effects of bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes on the value relevance of accounting information within Nigerian commercial banks and raise the following research question:

To what extent do bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes jointly influence the value relevance of accounting information of Nigerian commercial banks?

In light of the research question advanced above, the following hypothesis was formulated:

Ho: Bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes does not have significant joint influence on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigerian commercial banks.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents the conceptual review, review of empirical findings, and theoretical literature that sheds light on the intricate relationship between bank heterogeneity, CEO attributes and the value relevance of accounting information in the context of financial information of banks in Nigeria.

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Bank Heterogeneity

Bank heterogeneity encompasses the structural and operational differences that distinguish firms within the financial system. These variations arise from differences in size, ownership, business models, geographic reach, risk appetite, regulatory compliance, and strategic

orientation (Bernard et al., 2007; Bernard, Redding & Schott, 2007; Adão, Arkolakis & Ganapati, 2020). Understanding these differences is essential for policymakers, regulators, and market participants, as heterogeneity shapes competitive dynamics, investment behaviour, and the resilience of financial institutions to regulatory and economic shocks.

A central dimension of bank heterogeneity examined in prior research is bank size, given its influence on diversification capacity, access to funding, economies of scale, and exposure to systemic risk. Larger banks typically operate with broader portfolios, wider geographic coverage, and greater access to wholesale markets, enabling them to absorb shocks more effectively. Smaller banks, by contrast, tend to operate within niche or regional markets, making them more responsive to local conditions but more vulnerable to localized disturbances. In Nigeria, bank size is closely linked to licensing categories (such as international, national, or regional licenses), issued by the Central Bank of Nigeria, with minimum paid-up capital serving as a key differentiator.

Another important dimension of heterogeneity is business model orientation. Banks vary in their strategic focus, adopting retail, wholesale, investment, or universal banking models depending on their target markets and risk preferences. These models influence product offerings, customer segments, and revenue structures, thereby shaping the nature and complexity of financial reporting. Similarly, risk appetite and management practices differentiate banks, with some institutions adopting conservative strategies characterized by strong capital buffers, while others pursue more aggressive growth strategies with higher leverage and risk exposure (Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020; Ibekwe, 2021; Mbagwu & Obonofiemro, 2023).

Given these multifaceted differences, examining how bank heterogeneity shapes the value relevance of accounting information based on its interaction with CEO attributes is critical to understanding the financial health, resilience, and market valuation of Nigerian banks. Such insights are essential for informing regulatory policy, investor decision-making, and the broader strategic direction of the financial services sector.

2.1.2 CEO Attributes

Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) play a central role in organizational decision-making, and their actions are widely recognized as critical determinants of firm performance and firm value (Nguyen, Rahman & Zhao, 2017). As the top strategic leader, the CEO is responsible for setting organizational goals, formulating and executing strategies, monitoring performance, and making decisions that shape the firm's long-term viability. Effective CEO judgment is therefore essential, as organizational outcomes often reflect the quality of these strategic choices. CEOs who possess the requisite skills and experience are better positioned to steer their organizations toward achieving their stated vision and objectives.

Given this influence, prior studies highlight the need to pay close attention to CEO characteristics, which have been linked to various performance and reporting outcomes (Liu, Fisher & Chen, 2018; Rehman et al., 2021; Oyedokun, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2025). Research has examined attributes such as CEO tenure, professional expertise, ownership, age, education, gender, and turnover (Rehman et al., 2021; Lodikero, Soyinka & Sunday, 2022; Sinebe & Jeroh, 2023; Abata, Omorogbee & Adeyemi, 2023; Ukavwe & Jeroh, 2024). While substantial empirical attention has been devoted to the value relevance of accounting

information in Nigeria (Omokhudu & Ibadin, 2015; Chukwu, Damieibi & Okoye, 2019; Asogwa, Ofoegbu & Modum, 2020; Apete, Udeh & Ezekwesili, 2022), limited research has explored how CEO attributes shape the value relevance of financial information reported by Nigerian banks. Moreover, existing studies have not sufficiently examined whether bank heterogeneity moderates the relationship between CEO attributes and the value relevance of accounting information, a key gap this study seeks to address.

2.1.3. Concept of Value Relevance

Value relevance has become a central theme in accounting research due to its critical role in investment decision-making and capital market outcomes. It examines the extent to which information contained in financial statements explains or predicts a firm's market value, thereby influencing investors' perceptions and actions. Accounting information is considered value relevant when it contributes meaningfully to investors' judgments or affects stock prices and other indicators of economic worth (Oyedokun, 2019; Ighosewe, 2022; Ogieh & Jeroh, 2023). In essence, value relevance reflects how effectively key financial metrics such as earnings or book values reflects a firm's underlying fundamentals.

The usefulness of accounting information in this regard is largely determined by its relevance, reliability, and transparency. High-quality financial reporting enables investors to assess a firm's financial health, performance, and prospects, thereby supporting informed decision-making. For financial information to be value relevant, it must be timely, accurate, and prepared using consistent measurement and disclosure practices. Importantly, the concept of value relevance presupposes a reasonably efficient capital market in which publicly released financial information is rapidly incorporated into stock prices. Consequently, the degree to which variations in accounting numbers correspond with changes in share prices provides an empirical basis for evaluating value relevance (Omokhudu & Ibadin, 2015; Ikram, 2016; Chukwu, Damieibi & Okoye, 2019; Asogwa, Ofoegbu & Modum, 2020; Apete, Udeh & Ezekwesili, 2022; Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019).

Overall, assessments of value relevance must consider factors such as investor behavior, market efficiency, disclosure quality, and the broader institutional environment, all of which shape the extent to which financial reporting influences capital market outcomes.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Upper Echelons Theory (UET) and the Resource-Based View (RBV), which jointly provide a conceptual basis for understanding how CEO attributes and bank heterogeneity shape the value relevance of accounting information. Together, these theories explain how managerial characteristics and firm-specific resources influence strategic choices, financial reporting quality, and market valuations.

2.2.1 Upper Echelons Theory (UET)

The Upper Echelons Theory (Hambrick & Mason, 1984) posits that organizational outcomes reflect the backgrounds, experiences, and cognitive orientations of top executives. According to UET, CEOs' demographic and psychological characteristics such as age, tenure, education, expertise, and risk tolerance, shape how they interpret information and make strategic decisions. Operating under bounded rationality, executives filter complex realities through their personal values and cognitive biases, resulting in distinct managerial choices that influence firm performance, disclosure practices, and ultimately capital market outcomes.

In the context of financial reporting, UET suggests that variations in CEO attributes may lead to differences in the quality, transparency, and relevance of accounting information. Given that strategic reporting decisions are driven by managerial perceptions and priorities, UET provides a strong foundation for examining how CEO characteristics contribute to the value relevance of financial statements, particularly when considered alongside structural differences across banks.

2.2.2 Resource-Based View of Firms

The Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991) explains firm performance through the possession and effective deployment of valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources. RBV emphasizes that firms differ in their resource endowments—such as capital strength, technological capabilities, managerial expertise, and organizational culture—leading to heterogeneity in performance and competitive advantage.

Applied to the banking sector, RBV highlights how differences in size, technological infrastructure, market reach, and managerial competencies shape each bank's capacity to generate value and communicate this effectively through financial reports. CEO attributes constitute a key component of human capital, while broader bank heterogeneity represents distinct resource bundles that influence financial performance, risk management practices, and the credibility of reported information.

Thus, RBV provides a robust lens for understanding how banks' unique resource profiles and managerial capabilities jointly affect the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria's diverse banking environment.

2.3 Empirical Review

Empirical evidence on value relevance, bank heterogeneity, and CEO attributes reflects growing interest in understanding how firm characteristics and managerial factors influence the usefulness of accounting information. In Nigeria, several studies have examined the association between financial reporting variables and market outcomes. For instance, Enofe, Asiriwa, and Ashafoke (2014) found that accounting numbers significantly correlate with share prices, reinforcing the relevance of financial information to equity valuation. Similarly, Omokhodu and Ibadin (2015), using a modified Ohlson model, reported that earnings, cash flows, and dividends significantly explain firm value, whereas book value showed limited explanatory power in the Nigerian market. Evidence from the banking sector further shows that accounting metrics remain important indicators of share price movements. Olowolaju and Ogunsan (2016) demonstrated that book value per share, dividends, and earnings per share significantly predict share prices of listed banks, underscoring the value relevance of traditional accounting figures.

Other studies have focused on firm-level or reporting-specific factors influencing value relevance. Akadakpo and Mgbame (2018) observed that timeliness of reporting affects the market value of firms, with book value exhibiting the strongest explanatory power. In manufacturing firms, Ogbodo and Osisoma (2020) documented a strong relationship between dividend information and share prices, advocating for improved disclosure practices to sustain value relevance.

Research has also expanded to managerial and governance dimensions. Edi and Kho (2021) found that CEO reputation positively moderates the relationship between corporate governance and value relevance among Indonesian banks, suggesting that managerial credibility strengthens market perceptions of reported information. McCumber, Qiu, and Islam (2022) reported that CEO social capital increases investors' reliance on book value over earnings, indicating that CEO characteristics can shape investors' interpretation of accounting numbers. In Nigeria, Lateef et al. (2023) showed that CEOs' workload and tenure significantly influence financial reporting quality, highlighting human capital as a determinant of reporting outcomes.

Empirical evidence focused on CEO attributes and firm value also shows strong associations in emerging markets. Ukavwe and Jeroh (2024), examining non-financial firms in Nigeria, found that CEO gender, nationality, tenure, and ownership significantly influence firm value, implying that CEO characteristics shape strategic decisions and financial outcomes. Comparative studies (e.g., Busari et al., 2022) further reveal that accounting information remains value relevant in Nigeria, though with variation across sectors such as banking and insurance.

Collectively, these studies highlight that value relevance is shaped by both firm-specific attributes such as size, reporting practices, and sectoral dynamics and managerial characteristics. However, empirical research examining the joint influence of bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes on value relevance, particularly within the Nigerian banking sector, remains limited. This gap underscores the need for further investigation in environments marked by institutional diversity and complex leadership dynamics.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study employed an ex-post facto research design to examine the relationship between bank heterogeneity, CEO attributes, and the value relevance of accounting information among Nigerian commercial banks, a design considered appropriate because it allows observation of variables as they occur naturally and enhances external validity (Kothari & Garg, 2014). The population consisted of all 26 listed commercial banks in Nigeria as of December 31, 2023, from which a purposive sample of 11 banks was selected based on clearly defined criteria, including possession of a commercial banking license, continuous operation during the study period, availability of annual financial statements, and completeness of required data. Secondary data were extracted from publicly available financial statements of the sampled banks covering 2018–2022, a period noted for major regulatory reforms aimed at strengthening the financial system and expanding credit access, with likely implications for banks' market performance. Data analysis followed a quantitative approach involving descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation), correlation analysis, and appropriate diagnostic tests, while hypothesis testing was conducted using contemporaneous correlation with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) based on diagnostic outcomes.

3.5.1 Model Specification

The test of hypothesis in this study is based on the following model which have been specified to guide this study.

Model I

$$AQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BHetFugaz_{it} + \beta_2 BHetAuthl_{it} + \beta_3 CEXPT_{it} + \beta_4 CTEN_{it} + U_{it} \quad (1)$$

The subscripts i and t suggest a suggestion that the intercepts for the 11 banks may differ, but each of the bank's intercept does not vary over time. The *a-priori* expectation is that $\beta_1 X_{1it} < 0$, $\beta_2 X_{2it} < 0$, $\beta_3 X_{3it} < 0$ and $\beta_4 X_{4it} < 0$.

3.5.3 Measurement and Description of Variables

Variable Type	Variable	Proxy	Label	Measurement
Dependent Variable	Value Relevance	Share Price.	<i>SP</i>	Average share price for bank i in year t
Independent Variables	Bank Heterogeneity	FUGAZ Banks	<i>BHetFugaz</i>	Dummy variable of "1" is assigned where the bank is among the 5 biggest banks regarded as FUGAZ; otherwise "0".
		Authorization License	<i>BHetAuthl</i>	Where a bank has international authorization license, a dummy variable of "3" is assigned, while "2" is assigned where the bank has a national license and "1" is assigned where the bank has a regional authorization license.
	CEO Attributes	CEO Expertise	<i>CEXPT</i>	Dummy variable of "1" where the CEO has professional certification in addition to education certification in Accounting or related discipline, otherwise "0"
		CEO Tenure	<i>CTEN</i>	Dummy variable of 1 where the company's CEO has stayed for 3 years and above and "0" where the CEO has not served up to 3 years

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_3$ = Regressors
 it = Individual Banks at time t .
 ϵ = Error Term (variables not captured in the model)

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Presentation

This study examined how bank heterogeneity and the attributes of CEOs affects the value relevance of accounting information of Nigerian commercial banks. This study specifically focused on commercial banks in Nigeria given that banks are heavily regulated since several regulators oversee their operations at the same time. The data gathered for the analysis spanned five years (from 2018 to 2022)

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

This section contains the summary statistics that describe the type of data that was gathered for the study. The results examined in this section comprise the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values. The results for the descriptive statistics are shown in Table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
<i>SP</i>	55	12.24273	13.28226	0.55	47.95
<i>BHETFUGAZ</i>	55	0.45455	0.50252	0.00	1.00
<i>BHETAUTHL</i>	55	2.63636	0.48548	2.00	3.00
<i>CEXPT</i>	55	0.58182	0.49781	0.00	1.00
<i>CTEN</i>	55	0.76364	0.42876	0.00	1.00

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Based on the data in Table 4.1, the number of observations examined is 55. This is expected, because data from 11 banks over a period of 5 years should typically result in 55 observations, provided that the data collection yields a panel that is balanced. This however meets the threshold for the minimum number of observations needed for regression analysis which has always been 30 observations. Since the number of observations meets the minimum threshold, it means that the data qualifies to be subjected to regression analysis.

The mean values recorded for the variables ranged from 0.45455 (*BHETFUGAZ*) to 12.24273 (*SP*) with standard deviations that were relatively low having recorded the highest standard deviation of 13.28226 for share price (*SP*). The low standard deviations are indications of the presence of little variations in the data for the variables when compared to their respective overall average values. In terms of minimum values, share price (*SP*) recorded 0.55, bank heterogeneity in terms of bank’s inclusion as a FUGAZ bank (*BHETFUGAZ*) recorded 0; bank heterogeneity in terms of whether or not, the bank has international authorization license (*BHETAUTHL*) recorded 0; CEO expertise (*CEXPT*) recorded 2; whereas, CEO tenure (*CTEN*) recorded 0. With respect to the maximum values, *SP* recorded the highest value of 47.95; while *BHETAUTHL* had a maximum value of 3. In addition, *BHETFUGAZ*, *CEXPT* and *CTEN* recorded maximum values of 1 respectively. The nature of the results displayed above indicates that there are no cases of missing data for any of the variables.

4.2.2 Test For Normal Distribution of Data

The Shapiro-Wilk test for normal data was used to determine the distribution of the data and whether or not the data followed a normal curve. This is required to ascertain whether there are any contradictions with regards to the fundamental presumptions behind the application of the OLS regression method. Table 4.2 presents the result in this regard.

Table 4.2 Normality Test Outcome

Variables	Obs.	W	V	Z	Prob>Z
<i>SP</i>	55	0.78316	10.997	5.142	0.00000
<i>BHETFUGAZ</i>	55	0.99614	0.196	-3.495	0.99976
<i>BHETAUTHL</i>	55	0.98794	0.611	-1.055	0.85424
<i>CEXPT</i>	55	0.99602	0.202	-3.433	0.99970
<i>CTEN</i>	55	0.93916	3.085	2.416	0.00784

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

In line with the econometric requirements for test statistics, the residuals for any set of data are normally distributed at 0.05 (5%) significance level, provided that the probability values obtained for Z (Prob>Z) is more than (>) 0.05. When the Prob>Z obtained is less than 0.05, the implication is that such data set are not normally distributed. Based on this assertion, it is clear

from Table 4.2 that the data for *BHETFUGAZ*, *BHETAUTHL* and *CEXPT* produced Prob>Z values that are above the minimum required of 0.05 (0.99976, 0.85424 and 0.99970 respectively) meaning that the residuals of the dataset for these variables are normally distributed. Conversely, *SP* and *CTEN* produced Prob>Z values of 0.0000 and 0.00784 respectively. These values are less than the 0.05 minimum, thereby suggesting that the residuals of the dataset for share price and CEO tenure are not normally distributed.

Going by the above results, it is evident that the fundamental prerequisite of normality of residuals in dataset which must be met before applying the OLS regression technique when testing hypotheses has not been fully satisfied. As a result, using a more appropriate regression technique that will adjust for the standard errors included in the estimations becomes necessary. Nevertheless, it is appropriate to test for the correlation among the variables before further diagnostic tests could be conducted. The results in this regard is presented in the following section.

4.2.3 Correlation Analysis

Since the residuals for some of the data did not follow a normal distribution curve, the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho) was considered as a more appropriate correlation analysis tool to examine the relationship between bank heterogeneity, CEO attributes and the value relevance of accounting information of commercial banks in Nigeria. The Spearman rho result is therefore presented in Table 4.3 and analysed thereafter.

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

	SP	BHETFUGAZ	BHETAUTHL	CEXPT	CTEN
<i>SP</i>	1.0000				
<i>BHETFUGAZ</i>	0.5752* (0.0000)	1.0000			
<i>BHETAUTHL</i>	0.2787* (0.0394)	0.6901* (0.0000)	1.0000		
<i>CEXPT</i>	0.1905 (0.1637)	-0.3365* (0.0120)	-0.2577 (0.0575)	1.0000	
<i>CTEN</i>	-0.0876 (0.5246)	0.1641 (0.2313)	0.0243 (0.8604)	-0.0379 0.7838	1.0000

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

*significant at 5%

With the result of the correlation analysis presented in Table 4.3, the existence of a linear relationship could be established between share price (*SP*) and measures of the regressands (*BHETFUGAZ*, *BHETAUTHL*, *CEXPT* and *CTEN*). Note that the measures of CEO attributes (*CEXPT* and *CTEN*), exhibited weak correlation with *SP*; whereas, the measures of bank heterogeneity exhibited strong and positive correlation with *SP*. Also, it can be observed that the correlation between *CEXPT* and *SP* is positive, whereas, the correlation between *CTEN* and *SP* is negative. Notwithstanding, the correlation coefficient between pairs of the independent variables are in all cases below the maximum threshold of 0.80 which indicate the absence of possible indication of issues of multicollinearity. In order to confirm this, the dataset for these

variables were further subjected to the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test to ascertain whether multicollinearity is actually not present.

4.2.4 Tests for Multicollinearity and Heteroscedasticity

Table 4.4: Result for Multicollinearity Test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
<i>BHETFUGAZ</i>	2.10	0.476667
<i>BHETAUTHL</i>	1.94	0.515028
<i>CEXPT</i>	1.13	0.885353
<i>CTEN</i>	1.04	0.957776
Mean VIF	1.55	

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The values for VIF from the results in Table 4.4 ranged from 1.04 (for CTEN) to a 2.10 (for BHETFUGAZ) with a mean VIF of 1.55 which is below the maximum criterion of 10 (Jeroh, 2016; Jeroh, 2020; Jeroh & Ozegbe, 2022; Izukwe & Jeroh, 2022; Jeroh & Efeyunmi, 2022). This is a confirmation that the data used to measure the variables in this study do not have the problem of multicollinearity. This means that the inclusion of all the explanatory variables in the respective models would not yield unreliable outcomes.

Table 4.5: Heteroscedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan /Cook-Weisberg Test	
Chi2(1)	15.75
Prob > chi2	0.0001

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

With respect to the heteroscedasticity test, the chi2(1) value that was obtained was 15.75, while the corresponding probability value is 0.0001. This suggests that the variance in the residuals is not constant with the likely presence of standard errors in the estimations. The implication is that the dataset has heteroscedasticity concerns. With this outcome, it implies that the OLS regression method cannot suffice in the test of hypotheses; thus, requiring the application of a more appropriate statistical tool that has the capacity of addressing the problem of non-normality of residuals in the dataset with heteroscedasticity concern. For this purpose, the contemporaneous correlation technique that applies regression analysis with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) was employed for the test of the formulated hypotheses. Thus, in order to test the hypotheses earlier advanced, the contemporaneous correlation technique—which uses regression analysis with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE)—was used.

4.3. Test of Hypothesis and Discussion of Findings

Table 4.8: Result for Test of Hypothesis

SP	Coeff.	Panel-corrected Std. Err.	z	P > z	Decision
<i>BHETFUGAZ</i>	19.1495	2.1576	8.88	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
<i>BHETAUTHL</i>	-10.2656	1.5966	-6.43	0.000	
<i>CEXPT</i>	14.4379	.9558	15.11	0.000	
<i>CTEN</i>	-8.3429	4.0174	-2.08	0.038	
<i>_CONS</i>	28.5729	5.1221	5.58	0.000	
Obs.			55		
Wald chi2(2)			329.55		

Prob > chi2	0.0000
R-Squared	0.4486

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

*significant at 5%

In the test of Hypothesis Three, *BHETFUGAZ* and *CEXPT* recorded positive coefficients of 19.1495 and 14.4379 respectively; whereas, *BHETAUTHL* and *CTEN* were found to have recorded negative coefficients of -10.2656 and -8.3429 respectively. This means that *BHETFUGAZ* and *CEXPT* exhibits positive relationship with value relevance (SP), whereas, the reverse is the case for *BHETAUTHL* and *CTEN*. The result of the panel-corrected standard errors were found to be low with *CTEN* obtaining the highest value of 4.0174. The low values for the panel-corrected standard errors imply that the model for estimating the joint influence of bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes on value relevance of accounting information is precise and highly reliable.

The result of the z-statistics and the respective p-values indicate that all variables have the capacity of individually influencing the value relevance of accounting information. Overall, with the result of the Wald chi2 (2) of 329.55 with a corresponding probability value of 0.0000, it shows that at the 5% significance level, bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes exert joint significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information of commercial banks in Nigeria. With this outcome, the null hypothesis that bank heterogeneity and CEO attributes does not have significant joint influence on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigerian commercial banks is rejected by this study. This finding supports prior research evidence that CEO attributes are significant determinants of corporate attributes like firm value, performance measures and by extension, share price (see Rehman *et al.*, 2021; Lodikero, Soyinka & Sunday, 2022; Abata, Omorogbee & Adeyemi, 2023; Ukavwe & Jeroh, 2024)

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Bank heterogeneity as a concept and its interplay with CEO attributes and the value relevance of accounting information has become a topic of concern given the operational dimensions of Nigerian commercial banks and the increasing concern on how CEO characteristics affect the strategic dimension and business models adopted by banks generally in recent time. No doubt, given the level of competition in today's banking industry, it is expected that commercial banks will need to utilize their available and scarce resources to explore options that could give them advantage over their competitors while experiencing boost in their overall performance and value without neglecting the overall trends of share price movements. It is interesting to note that while researches have primarily concentrated on probing the relationship between CEO attributes and performance and/or firm value, our appraisal of the apposite literature revealed aptly that studies have not examined the interconnection between bank heterogeneity, CEO attributes and the value relevance of entities with particular attention to only listed Nigerian commercial banks. The results from the test of hypothesis however proved that in Nigeria, the diversity in the dimensions of banks' operational activities and business models in addition to size and market share which in this study was captured as bank heterogeneity, is a significant determinant of share price movement which was used to measure the value relevance of accounting information.

Based on these outcomes of this study, it was recommended that:

- i. Commercial banks should always align the selection of CEOs with their specific strategic objectives and capitalize on their CEOs' unique strengths and attributes to drive competitive advantage and enhance value relevance of accounting information.
- ii. Banks should invest in continuous training and professional development for CEOs and top management, focusing on emerging financial trends, regulatory changes, and ethical leadership. This will help align CEO decisions with the long-term interests of the bank and its stakeholders.

REFERENCES

- Abata, M. A., Omorogbee, G. & Adeyemi, B. S. (2023). CEO demographics attributes and earnings management: evidence from Nigerian listed Deposit Money Banks. *FUOYE Journal of Accounting and Management*, 6(2), 1-52.
- Adão, R., Arkolakis, C. & Ganapati, S. (2020). Aggregate implications of firm heterogeneity: A nonparametric analysis of monopolistic competition trade models. *NBER Working Paper Series: Paper No: 28081*, 1-71.
- Akadakpo, B. A. & Mgbame, M. C. (2018). Value relevance of accounting information: The moderating effect of timeliness. *Accounting & Taxation Review*, 2(1), 122-135
- Apete, C.; Udeh, F. N. & Ezekwesili, T. P. (2022). Value relevance of accounting information and share price of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Management Practice*, 2(1), 11-28.
- Asogwa, C. I., Ofoegbu, G. N. & Modum, U. (2020). Effect of corporate governance on income persistence and value relevance of quoted Nigerian firms. *African Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 7(1), 42-65.
- Bernard, A. B., Jensen, J. B., Redding, S. J. & Schott, P. K. (2007). Firms in international trade. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 21(3), 105-30.
- Bernard, A. B., Redding, S. J. & Schott, P. K. (2007). Comparative Advantage and Heterogeneous Firms. *Review of Economic Studies*, 74, 31-66.
- Busari, K., Chechet, I. L., Abdullahi, A. A. & Mohammed, I. (2022). Value relevance of accounting information for listed financial service firms in Nigeria. *Gusau Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 3(3), 87-101.
- CBN (2024). List of Deposit Money Banks as at April 26, 2024. Available at https://r.search.yahoo.com/_ylt=AwrEqzZ1hs9m9wMANFJXNyoA;_ylu=Y29sbwNiZjEEcG9zAzUEdnRpZAMEc2VjA3Ny/RV=2/RE=1726086007/RO=10/RU=https%3a%2f%2fwww.cbn.gov.ng%2fOut%2f2024%2fCCD%2fLIST%2520OF%2520DEPOSIT%2520MONEY%2520BANKS%2520AS%2520AT%252026TH%2520APRIL%2c%25202024%2520%281%29.pdf/RK=2/RS=o2UUzHdRiAFgmh_x995EvDGFHil-

- Chukwu, G. J., Damieibi, I. J. & Okoye, E. I. (2019). Firm-Specific Attributes and the Value Relevance of Accounting Information in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 14(10), 12-20.
- Enofe, A. O., Asiriwa, O. & Ashafoke, T. O. (2014). Value relevance of accounting information in the banking sub-sector of the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE). *British Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 1(1), 42-55.
- Gupta, N. J. & Mahakud, J. (2020). Ownership, bank size, capitalization and bank performance: Evidence from India. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 8(1), 1-39. DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2020.1808282.
- Ibekwe, A. O. (2021). Financial innovation and performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 9(1), 162-173.
- Ighosewe, E. F. (2022). Accounting information and value relevance: A quinquennial comparison of pre-and post-IFRS adoption of listed firms in Nigeria and South Africa. *Modern Economy*, 13(7), 1006-1023.
- Ikram, Z. (2016). Corporate governance and value relevance of accounting information: Evidence from Pakistan. *M.Sc. Thesis, Capital University of Science and Technology Islamabad*. Available at <https://thesis.cust.edu.pk/UploadedFiles/Zahid%20Ikram-MM141018.pdf>
- Inim, V. E., Njogo, B. O. & Oladele, J. A. (2019). Banking reforms and the stability of the Nigerian banking system. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 1(6), 1-10.
- Izukwe, R. & Jeroh, E. (2022). Auditors' attributes and firm value of listed Nigerian service firms. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal* 4(4), 218-230
- Jeroh, E. & Efeyunmi, P. M. (2022). Diligence and independence of corporate board committees and the quality of reported earnings among listed companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics* 14(3), 501-526.
- Jeroh, E. (2016). Effect of IFRS adoption on the determinants of share prices in quoted service firms in Nigeria. *Sahel Analyst: Journal of Management Science* 14(4), 1-12
- Jeroh, E. (2020). An assessment of the internal determinants of the environmental disclosure practices of firms across Sub-Saharan Africa. *Ekonomski Horizonti*, 22(1), 47-59.
- Kothari, C. R., & Garg, G. (2014). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International.
- Lateef, S. A., Rasheed, N. Olanipekun, W. D., Ado, A. B. & Mustapha, U. A. (2023) Do CEO attributes influence financial reporting quality of listed firms in Nigeria? Using bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development*, 44(2), 159-184.
- Liu, D., Fisher, G., & Chen, G. (2018). CEO attributes and firm performance: A sequential mediation process model. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 12(2), 789–816. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2016.0031>

- Lodikero, O., Soyinka, K. A. & Sunday, O. M. (2022). Chief Executive Officers (CEO) attributes and earnings management of listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 6(12), 234-239.
- Mbagwu, O. N. & Obonofiemro, G. (2023). Technological disruption and Deposit Money Banks financial performance in the pre and post covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(4), 218-232.
- McCumber, W. R., Qiu, H. & Islam, M. S. (2022). CEO social capital and the value relevance of accounting metrics: International evidence. *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 19, (4), 80-102
- Naburigi, M.M., Ojo, L.O., & Oyedokun, G.E. (2024). Board Attributes and Risk Disclosure of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies Listed in Nigerian Exchange Group. *Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)*, 9(1), 40-56, a publication of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
- Nguyen, P., Rahman, N. & Zhao, R. (2017). CEO characteristics and firm valuation: A quantile regression analysis. *Journal of Management and Governance*, 22, 133-151. DOI 10.1007/s10997-017-9383-7.
- Ogbodo, O. C. & Osisoma, B. C. (2020). Value relevance of accounting information and share price: An empirical study on manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research (Social and Management Sciences)*, 6(12), 64-77.
- Ogieh, A. S. & Jeroh, E. (2023). Corporate governance and the value relevance of earnings. *Himalayan Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(5), 55-63.
- Olowolaju, P.S. & Ogunsan, J. O. (2016). value relevance of accounting information in the determination of shares prices of quoted Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*4(10), 128-147.
- Omokhudu, O. & Ibadin, P. (2015). The value relevance of accounting information: Evidence from Nigeria. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 4(3), 20-30.
- Oyedokun, G. E. (2019). Board characteristics and financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Accounting & Taxation review*, official Journal of the International Accounting and Taxation Research Group, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Benin, Nigeria.
- Oyedokun, G. E., & Nwaokolobia, B. O. & Andah, A, R. (2019). Board gender diversity and performance of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Financial Sustainability Reporting (RJFSR)* 4(2), 1-12. A publication of the Department of Accountancy, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science & Technology
- Oyedokun, G. E., Micah, E. E. M., & Gimba, J.T. (2020). Effect of Board Attributes on Dividend Policies of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. A paper presented at British Academy of Management BAM2020 Conference at Alliance Manchester Business School, Manchester, United Kingdom, 2-4 September 2020.
- Oyedokun, G.E., Oyedokun, D.M., & Oyedokun, P.O., (2025). Cultural Communication and Stakeholders' Engagement in the Nigerian Financial Reporting Landscape: A Two-Decade Contextual Analysis. In. K.A. Adeyemo, O. Campbell & O. Adepoju (Eds.). Two Decade of Lead City University, Ibadan: Management and Social Sciences Perspective to contemporary

- issues in Nigeria. A publication of the Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan. 41- 56. ISBN-978-978-775-786-4
- Ozegbe, K. K. & Jeroh, E. (2022). Audit quality and the financial performance of quoted companies in Nigeria: Empirical discourse. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Economica* 18(5), 182-197.
- Rehman, A. Jun, J. C., Rehman, A, Zeeshan, M., Adeel, M., Saleem, K. & Rehman, S. U. (2021). Unravelling the Nexus Between CEO Characteristics and Financial Performance in Pakistani Listed Firms *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(6), 65-91.
- Sinebe, M. T. & Jeroh, E. (2023). Corporate governance and financial statements' fraud: Evidence from listed firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Management and Commerce*, 4(2), 118-123.
- Souhir, N. & Amal, A. (2022). The effect of CEO's attributes and Zakat on the performance of Islamic banks. *Journal of Accounting, Ethics & Public Policy*, 23(4), 609 -628.
- Ukavwe, G. & Jeroh, E. (2024). Chief Executive Officer (CEO) attributes and the value of quoted firms in Nigeria. *Finance and Accounting Research Journal*, 6(6), 911-930.
- Umar-Dauda, S. L. & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Impact assessment of tax audit on tax compliance: A case study of Katsina State Board of Internal Revenue. *AE-FUNAI Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance (FJABAF)*, 3(1), 54-61. A bi-annual Journal of the Department of Accountancy, Business and Administration, Banking & Finance, Alex-Ekwueme Federal University of Ndufu-Alike, Ebonyi State Nigeria. Available at <https://www.fujabf.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/5.pdf>